

IBERIFIER

Iberian Media Research
& Fact-Checking

IBERIFIER

Three Years Combating Disinformation

February 2024

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Joining Forces Against Disinformation

Ramón Salaverría, Coordinator of IBERIFIER

Disinformation poses a global threat. To tackle it, it is necessary to join efforts and collaborate from multiple areas.

Promoted by the European Commission, the IBERIFIER observatory has been gathering since 2021 in Spain and Portugal 23 public and private organisations of academic research, news agencies and fact-checking, and strategic analysis.

Our work, reflected in multiple reports and dissemination activities, has allowed us to better understand the nature, dimensions, and impacts of disinformation in the Iberian territory. It has identified technologies to address the problem and has revealed the characteristics of the digital information ecosystem in our two countries. Additionally, it has promoted multiple awareness and education initiatives for the citizens against false content and hate speech.

IBERIFIER is part of the hubs' network that covers the 27 EU countries, under the coordination of the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). Having completed our first stage, we will continue with our work to combat disinformation, in favor of society. ■

La desinformación representa una amenaza global. Para enfrentarla, es preciso sumar esfuerzos y colaborar desde múltiples ámbitos. Promovido por la Comisión Europea, el observatorio IBERIFIER reúne desde 2021 en España y Portugal a 23 organizaciones públicas y privadas de investigación académica, agencias de noticias y verificación, y análisis estratégico.

Nuestro trabajo, reflejado en múltiples informes y actividades de difusión, ha permitido comprender mejor la naturaleza, dimensiones e impactos de la desinformación en el territorio ibérico. Ha identificado tecnologías para enfrentar el problema y ha revelado las características del ecosistema de la información digital en nuestros dos países. Además, ha impulsado múltiples iniciativas de sensibilización y educación de la ciudadanía contra los contenidos falsos y los discursos de odio.

IBERIFIER forma parte de la red de centros que abarca los 27 países de la UE, bajo la coordinación del European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). Completada nuestra primera etapa, continuaremos con nuestra labor de lucha contra la desinformación, en favor de la sociedad. ■

A desinformação representa uma ameaça global. Para enfrentá-la, é necessário somar esforços e colaborar em diversas frentes. Promovido pela Comissão Europeia, o observatório IBERIFIER reúne desde 2021, em Espanha e em Portugal, 23 organizações públicas e privadas de investigação académica, agências de notícias e verificação, e análise estratégica.

O nosso trabalho, refletido em múltiplos relatórios e atividades de divulgação, tem-nos permitido compreender melhor a natureza, dimensões e impactos da desinformação no território ibérico. Identificou tecnologias para enfrentar o problema e revelou as características do ecossistema de informação digital nos dois países. Além disso, impulsionou múltiplas iniciativas de sensibilização e educação da cidadania contra conteúdos falsos e discursos de ódio.

O IBERIFIER faz parte da rede de centros que abrange os 27 países da UE, sob a coordenação do European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). Concluída esta primeira etapa, continuaremos o nosso trabalho de combate à desinformação, em favor da sociedade. ■

01

IBERIFIER

IBERIFIER is a digital media observatory in Spain and Portugal, funded by the European Commission and linked to the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO).

Coordinated by the University of Navarra, it is made up of twelve universities, five fact-checking organizations and news agencies, and six multidisciplinary research centers.

Its main mission is to analyze the Iberian digital media ecosystem and tackle the problem of misinformation. To do this, it focuses its research on five lines of work:

01

Research on the characteristics and trends of the Iberian digital media ecosystem.

02

Preparation of strategic reports on disinformation threats in multiple fields at Spain and Portugal.

03

Research on AI and computer technology for the early detection of misinformation.

04

Promotion of media literacy initiatives, aimed at journalists, young people and society as a whole.

05

Fact-checking of mis- and disinformation in the Iberian territory.

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- 14 Lusa
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- 15 Maldita.es
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- 16 Newtral
Madrid, Spain [collaborator]
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- 18 Prova dos Factos - Público
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Madrid, Spain
- 24 OberCom - Observatório da Comunicação
Lisboa, Portugal
- 25 Real Instituto Elcano
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02

Digital Media Research

Composed of 10 research institutions specialized in the analysis of the media industry from different perspectives, our Digital Media Research team focuses on exploring the characteristics and trends of the Iberian digital news media ecosystem.

Iberian Digital Media Map

It identifies and characterizes the existing models of digital news in Spain and Portugal, providing strategic references for the media industry, the scientific community and other relevant stakeholders.

Digital news and disinformation consumption patterns

The report provides an in-depth analysis of disinformation consumption patterns in Spain and Portugal. It focuses on sources of news, trust in various media, and public perception of disinformation. The findings highlight a significant reliance on television for news, varying levels of trust in different news sources, and a notable concern about disinformation, especially in online environments.

Business aspects of disinformation

Exploration of the dynamics and effects of disinformation on the media industry in Spain and Portugal, providing an overview of the challenges

and opportunities that disinformation poses for journalists, media organizations, and the public.

Digital News Report (Spain & Portugal)

The 'Digital News Report' is an annual publication by the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism at the University of Oxford. Our national reports aim to understand how news is being consumed in the digital age in Spain and Portugal.

Legal and political aspects of disinformation

The political sphere has proven to be a fertile ground for the generation and propagation of disinformation. IBERIFIER has identified six specific topics and moments in recent history, between 2020 and 2023, and associated with the spread of disinformation, that have raised doubts and mistrust among citizens. Our research also includes legislation on the fight against disinformation, from the European to the local level, on both the Portuguese and Spanish sides.

Fact-checking trends

In-depth examination of the fact-checking landscape in Spain and Portugal. It analyzes the verification initiatives of major media outlets and independent agencies, highlighting their methodologies, engagement strategies, and the challenges they face in the digital era.

Innovation trends in digital media

Comprehensive analysis of the emerging trends and innovations shaping the media landscape in Spain and Portugal from 2025 to 2030. It emphasizes the pivotal role of Artificial Intelligence in transforming content creation, distribution, and journalistic processes, alongside the growing significance of Big Data and blockchain technology.

03

Fact-checking

Our observatory pioneers an Iberian alliance of fact-checking organizations, forming a core part of a global expert hub. We maintain a dynamic repository of fact-checks, averaging 80 monthly contributions, aiding EDMO’s extensive collection. Our advanced tools automate data gathering of misinformation, enhancing our robust alert system that pinpoints and reports disinformation campaigns, integrating with Ibero-American platforms to bolster a network spanning over 21 countries, ensuring factual integrity across the media landscape.

▲ IBERIFIER Quarterly Reports

IBERIFIER’s fact-checking team collects the main hoaxes and disinformation narratives detected in Spain and Portugal.

▲ EDMO Monthly Briefs

EDMO’s Fact-checking Briefs provide an overview of the disinformation narratives with highest circulations in the month previous to publication.

- Documents prove that Alexander Soros backed a deal between Western companies and Kiev authorities to dispose toxic waste in Ukraine.
- 18 European countries have issued a statement against a Spanish law that will annulity Catalan independence who were convicted after the prosecution ceased in 2017, and stated that European funds be taken away from Spain if it is approved.
- The Jewish celebration of Hanukkah is a Satanic holiday.
- US and France requested Greece to accommodate over 100,000 displaced Palestinian refugees from Gaza.

04

Computer & Data Research

IBERIFIER’s researchers from the Computer and Data Research team combine technological expertise and fact-checking to battle disinformation, merging advanced AI, machine learning, and computational methods. This involves researching and deploying innovative tools for monitoring, tracing, and analyzing disinformation on digital platforms. The initiative also focuses on developing guidelines, best practices, and infrastructures to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of fact-checking processes and to systematically collect and analyze disinformation data, aiding in the exposure of its characteristics and propagation patterns.

Is the ‘AI toolbox for disinformation’ ready?

This report assesses the readiness of the ‘AI toolbox’ for disinformation, highlighting the pervasive challenge of distinguishing reliable from malicious content online. It emphasizes the potential of computational methods and AI in understanding and mitigating disinformation, but notes a significant gap between AI advancements and their practical application in combatting disinformation. The report serves as a concise guide through recent AI literature, focusing on Machine Learning techniques and their application in disinformation analysis, especially within the Iberian research community.

Needs and Challenges for Iberian Fact-checkers

This IBERIFIER report focuses on Iberian fact-checkers, detailing their current situation and the technological and training needs essential for combating misinformation effectively in Spain and Portugal. It emphasizes the fact-checkers’ interest in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) to enhance their workflow and the necessity for specialized tools like social network analysis and advanced video editing software. Additionally, it underlines the importance of understanding AI’s limitations and ethical considerations, advocating for integrating human judgment with technology to ensure responsible use.

05

Strategic analysis

IBERIFIER provides strategic analysis on disinformation's impact across politics, economy, society, security, science, technology, and media industries. Leveraging expert insights, it offers in-depth evaluations and actionable recommendations to mitigate disinformation's adverse effects and foster a robust, secure digital media ecosystem in the Iberian region. This comprehensive approach ensures a multifaceted understanding and response to the complex challenges posed by disinformation.

Impact of Disinformation on Social Perception of Science and Technology in Spain ▾

Analysis of the prevalence and perception of scientific disinformation in Spain, exploring public engagement with science-related content and the trustworthiness of various information channels. This report emphasizes the critical need for discernment in the digital age, where the blending of accurate and misleading information can significantly influence public opinion and behavior.

Impact of Disinformation on the Media Industries Ecosystem

This report explores articles and publications that mention key terms such as "disinformation" or "fake-news". The objective is to uncover patterns, themes, and narratives employed by digital media in these two countries to inform, warn, and educate their audiences about the challenges posed by misleading information.

Analysis of the Impact of Disinformation on Political, Economic, Social and Security Issues, Governance Models and Good Practices: The cases of Spain and Portugal ▸

This report discusses the challenges posed by disinformation, explores media market specificities, digitalization, and the phenomenon of political polarization. It also evaluates the financial sustainability

of media, trust levels, and presents case studies exemplifying the media and political challenges in countering disinformation, emphasizing the varied trust relationships with national media in the two countries.

06

Media literacy

The Media Literacy, dissemination, and communication team has a multifaceted approach aimed at enhancing public understanding and awareness of disinformation's impact.

It leverages a range of educational tools, media platforms, and targeted training to equip stakeholders, educators, and the broader community with the knowledge and skills needed to identify and counter disinformation effectively. In addition to education and awareness campaigns, IBERIFIER places a strong emphasis on research and development, creating a robust foundation of knowledge through publications, reports, and digital innovations. These efforts are designed to not only inform but also actively involve various societal sectors, ensuring a comprehensive and collaborative approach to tackling disinformation.

Cabo Verde, September 2022

Pontevedra, April 2023

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